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A FORWARD SELECTION-BASED ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK APPROACH FOR STOCK PRICE FORECASTING

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Abstract

The volatile nature of stock prices, influenced by various internal and external factors, makes forecasting stock prices a complex challenge. Consequently, an approach is needed that can generate accurate and stable predictions to support investment decision-making.

Advances in artificial intelligence technology, particularly machine learning and artificial neural networks (ANNs), offer alternatives for modeling complex, non-linear patterns in time-series data. One widely used ANN model is the multilayer perceptron (MLP). The quality of the input features highly influences the performance of the MLP model. This study integrates the Forward Selection (FS) feature selection method to improve the MLP model's performance in stock price forecasting. The experimental results show that the individual MLP model has captured data patterns quite well. However, the model's performance improved significantly after integration with the Forward Selection method. The best model achieved an R^2 of 0.8658, a Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 0.0331, and a Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) of 0.0462, outperforming individual neural network models.

Keywords: Artificial Neural Network, Forward Selection, Stock Price Forecasting, Integration of Forward Selection and Artificial Neural Network

1. Introduction

Stock market trends have become a major driver of investment. The right stock investments can yield significant returns (Wang et al., 2023). However, fluctuating or unstable stock prices can cause anxiety among investors (Suripto, 2023). Investors are seeking a decision-making system to predict a company's stock price.

Stock price analysis and prediction are among the most challenging tasks in the financial world. Market direction predictions are often unstable and difficult to rely on consistently due to the ever-changing nature of market data, which is influenced by numerous variables—both internal to the issuer and external macroeconomic factors and market sentiment (Lakshmi et al., 2022). Various approaches have been employed, ranging from fundamental and technical analysis to time-series and statistical methods. While these methods can help explain price behavior, no single approach consistently serves

as the most reliable predictive tool across diverse market conditions (Singh et al., 2024). Stock price prediction methods can serve as the foundation for a decision support system.

Information technology is advancing rapidly. This is particularly evident in the use of artificial intelligence (AI), which includes machine learning and data mining. In machine learning, various models, methods, and algorithms are widely used in daily life across fields such as healthcare, agriculture, and economics. One of its applications is time-series forecasting. Several literature reviews indicate that ML algorithms often outperform traditional statistical methods in certain contexts due to their ability to learn non-linear patterns and complex interactions among variables (Khadka & Karki, 2024; Nath & Shakhari, 2023). Advances in financial technology (FinTech) have also strengthened the data processing ecosystem, from data acquisition to prediction generation, thereby accelerating AI research for stock price forecasting (Kakkar et al., 2024).

Numerous studies have been conducted by researchers on stock price prediction using artificial neural networks (ANNs). The ANN method is capable of modeling nonlinear relationships in time series. Various studies have shown that the ANN method is more adaptive compared to statistical techniques. Mahfuzh and Yuliantari (2022) applied ANN to forecast stock prices on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). The results of the study showed that ANN achieved a relatively low prediction error rate, making it effective for stock price forecasting based on historical data.

Saputra and Suharsono (2025) used the ANN method to predict the stock price of PT Bank Central Asia Tbk in Indonesia. This study confirmed that ANNs can effectively recognize price movement patterns in banking company stocks and provide fairly accurate predictions. Aryanti et al. (2023) investigated the use of ANNs for predicting stock prices. The results show that the ANN model can optimally adjust network weights during training, thereby improving prediction performance compared to linear methods.

With advancements in data acquisition and preprocessing technologies across many financial fields, high-dimensional datasets with many features, including irrelevant ones, are being generated. This situation can increase computational complexity and heighten the risk of overfitting, leading to a decline in prediction performance on new data. Therefore, feature selection is a crucial data preprocessing step for filtering the most informative features while discarding variables that do not aid the model, thereby making the model more efficient, more stable, and easier to interpret (Bommert et al., 2020; Chiregi et al., 2025; El Touati et al., 2024; Otchere et al., 2022).

Feature selection aims to reduce the input dimension while retaining important information relevant to the prediction target. Its impact extends not only to improved performance but also to reduced computational load and enhanced interpretability (Liapis et al., 2025). This study aims to integrate the Forward Selection method to improve the performance of ANN models, particularly MLP models, in stock price forecasting.

2. Related Work

Many researchers have researched forecasting. Researchers have conducted studies in various fields and used a wide range of forecasting methods. The forecasting methods used include ARIMA, Exponential Smoothing, Moving Average, and Machine Learning methods, particularly Neural Networks. These methods have also been successfully applied to stock price forecasting.

Funde & Damani (2023) conducted a study comparing the performance of the ARIMA and Exponential Smoothing models in forecasting stock prices of several companies in the NIFTY 50 index. The evaluation assessed the performance of the forecasting methods using error metrics such as RMSE and MAPE. The researchers generated forecasts with both ARIMA and exponential smoothing models and compared the results using RMSE and MAPE.

Saputra & Suharsono (2025) successfully used an ANN model to predict the stock price of PT Bank Central Asia Tbk. This study confirms that ANNs can effectively recognize price movement patterns in banking companies and provide accurate predictions. Widhi Aryanti & Nur Azizah Komara Rifai (2023) also utilized an ANN model for stock price forecasting. The study's results further demonstrated that the ANN model can optimally adjust network weights during training and improve forecasting performance compared to linear methods. These studies indicate that ANNs are effective at modeling stock price forecasts for the dynamic banking sector.

Bao et al. (2025) conducted a comprehensive review of data-driven neural networks in stock forecasting. The methods used in this study include a comprehensive review of existing literature on data-driven neural network models for stock forecasting, an evaluation of these models' performance in stock market forecasting, and an overview of evaluation metrics commonly used in the field. The methods used in this study include a comprehensive review of 63 journal and conference articles from 2015 to 2023. The results of this study indicate that data-driven Neural Networks are effective in stock price forecasting.

Jin (2025) conducted research exploring the nonlinear mapping relationship between historical stock data and the next day's closing price using a Backpropagation Neural Network (BPNN) model. The findings of this study indicate that the BPNN model demonstrates strong forecasting capabilities in stable markets, and extending the time horizon can improve prediction accuracy. This study achieved a BPNN model performance with an R^2 of up to 0.96.

3. Proposed Methodology

This research process includes data collection, data preprocessing, neural network modeling, neural network integration, feature selection using forward selection, and evaluation. Figure 1 illustrates the methodology used in this study.

Figure 1. Proposed Method

3.1 Dataset used

This study uses a dataset to evaluate the performance of a neural network model and its integration with the forward-selection feature-selection method. All datasets consist of daily stock price time series data collected from 2023 to 2025. The dataset used consists of daily stock prices for BCA (Bank Central Asia), sourced from <https://finance.yahoo.com/quote/BBCA.JK/> (Yahoo Finance, 2026).

3.2 Data Pre-processing

After collecting the data, we performed preprocessing to reduce noise. The data preprocessing steps included: using univariate stock time series data, checking for and handling missing values, normalizing the data, and applying windowing to the time series data.

a. Using univariate time series stock data

The dataset used consists of daily univariate time series data, specifically Date and Close values.

b. Handling missing values

In this step, we checked whether the data contained missing values. The missing values checked were those that were empty or null. If missing values were found, they were replaced using the forward-fill method or the Last Observation Carried Forward (LOCF) method, which involves filling the missing value at time t with the last available value before t (Usmani et al., 2024).

c. Performing data normalization

The researcher then performs data normalization on the dataset. This is used to eliminate data duplication, reduce data complexity, and facilitate data modification. The normalization used is the min-max equation (Mandal et al., 2020).

$$X' = \frac{X - X_{min}}{X_{max} - X_{min}} \quad (1)$$

Where X' is the new data, X is the input data, X_{min} is the data corresponding to the smallest value of X , and X_{max} is the data corresponding to the largest value of X .

d. Performing windowing on univariate time series data.

The univariate time series dataset is then divided into input data and output/target data. The transformation of univariate time series data into multivariate data is illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1. Transformation of Univariate Time Series Data into Multivariate Data

Pattern	<i>Lags-1</i>	<i>Lags-2</i>	<i>Lags-3</i>	...	<i>Lags-p</i>	Target
1	x_1	x_2	x_3	...	x_p	x_{p+1}
2	x_2	x_3	x_4	...	x_{p+1}	x_{p+2}
...
m-p	x_{m-p}	x_{m-p+1}	x_{m-p+2}	...	x_{m-1}	x_m

Table 1 shows that the features lag-1, lag-2, lag-3, ..., lag-p are used as input and target variables in the neural network model (Purwanto et al., 2011). In this study, we use lag-1, lag-2, lag-3, ..., lag-7 as input features and lag-8 as the target variable.

3.3 Feature Selection

The feature selection method used is Forward Selection. By removing irrelevant features, the model is expected to focus more on patterns that truly influence the target. This is expected to improve prediction performance on new data or test data.

3.4 Neural Network Model

After normalizing the data, we split the dataset. The data was divided into two parts: training and testing. In this study, the training and testing data were split into 80% and 20%, respectively (Gülmez, 2023; Teixeira & Barbosa, 2025).

The architecture neural network used is a multilayer perceptron (MLP). The MLP architecture used is as follows:

1. Input layer: receives lag_{t-1} , lag_{t-2} , lag_{t-3} , ..., lag_{t-7} as input layer neurons
2. Hidden layer: one or more layers that apply linear transformations and non-linear activations.

In this study, one or more hidden layers with varying numbers of neurons are used.

3. Output layer: generates the prediction (lag_t)

The MLP architecture used in this study is illustrated in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. MLP architecture with 7 input neurons and 1 output neuron

The equations in the MLP model are calculated using the following formula (Suhartono, 2008):

$$y(x) = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^H \beta_j \Psi(\gamma_{j0} + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_{ji} x_i) , \tag{2}$$

Where $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_H$, and $\gamma_{10}, \dots, \gamma_{Hn}$ are the weights of the MLP, n is the number of features, and H is the number of hidden layers.

3.5 Integration of the Neural Network Model with Forward Selection

The neural network model was also integrated with forward selection for stock prediction. Feature selection was used to determine which features influence the target variable.

3.6 Evaluation

The final stage of this study is the evaluation stage. In this stage, the researcher evaluates the performance of the Neural Network model on an individual basis, without feature selection. Next, the performance of integrating Forward Selection with the Neural Network model is also evaluated. For the evaluation, we use the following equation.

- a. RMSE (*Root Mean Square Error*) (Mandal et al., 2020)

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_t - \hat{Y}_t)^2}{n}} \tag{3}$$

Where Y_t is the actual stock data, \hat{Y}_t is the predicted stock data in the testing set of size n .

- b. MSE (*Mean Squared Error*) (Mandal et al., 2020)

$$MSE = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (Y_t - \hat{Y}_t)^2}{n} \tag{4}$$

Where Y_t is the actual stock data, \hat{Y}_t is the predicted stock data in the testing set of size n.

c. Determination Coefficient

The coefficient of determination (R^2) is a statistical measure used to evaluate how well a model explains the variation in a dependent variable based on independent variables. R^2 can be mathematically calculated as:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{SS_{res}}{SS_{tot}} \tag{5}$$

Where SS_{res} is the sum of squared residuals, and SS_{tot} is the total sum of squares. The R^2 value ranges from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating better model performance. According to Gao (2024), the R^2 value is the most commonly used measure in regression to evaluate the goodness of fit, that is, the extent to which the model can represent the observed data.

4. Results and Discussion

This study uses a dataset with the attributes Date and Close. The univariate time series dataset of BCA stock prices used in this study is illustrated graphically as follows:

Figure 3. Chart of Closing Stock Prices Used

Figure 3 shows an overall upward trend in BCA’s stock closing price during the 2023–2025 period, despite some fluctuations. The BCA stock closing price chart shows the movement of the closing price from the beginning of 2023 to the end of 2025. After checking the data, there were no missing values. After applying Min-Max scaling, all values in the ‘Close’ feature were scaled to the range [0, 1] and stored in a new column named 'Close_Normalized'. The example datasets of normalizing the BCA stock closing price are shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Dataset of the BCA Stock Closing Prices and 'Close_Normalized'

No	Date	Close	Close_Normalized
1	2023-01-02	7,820.3452	0.187339
2	2023-01-03	7,820.3452	0.187339
3	2023-01-04	7,637.4131	0.131881
4	2023-01-05	7,545.9468	0.104153
5	2023-01-06	7,591.6802	0.118017
6	2023-01-09	7,728.8794	0.159610
7	2023-01-10	7,477.3472	0.083356
8	2023-01-11	7,431.6143	0.069492
9	2023-01-12	7,477.3472	0.083356
10	2023-01-13	7,363.0146	0.048695
11	2023-01-16	7,454.4805	0.076424
12	2023-01-17	7,614.5464	0.124949
13	2023-01-18	7,591.6802	0.118017
14	2023-01-19	7,614.5464	0.124949
15	2023-01-20	7,591.6802	0.118017
16	2023-01-24	7,523.0806	0.097220
17	2023-01-25	7,500.2134	0.090288
18	2023-01-26	7,751.7451	0.166542
19	2023-01-27	7,957.5444	0.228932

The target variable is Close_Normalized, the normalized closing price of the BCA stock. This study uses a 7-day lag, meaning it considers the normalized closing prices from the previous 7 days. Regarding the data structure, Close_Normalized_lag_1 contains the Close_Normalized value from 1 day prior; Close_Normalized_lag_2 contains the Close_Normalized value from 2 days prior; and so on up to Close_Normalized_lag_7, which contains the Close_Normalized value from 7 days prior.

This dataset is then used to train a neural network model that learns from historical patterns to predict future stock prices. The windowing process for the BCA stock closing price dataset is shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Windowing Process for the BCA's Closing Stock Price (20 data)

No	X_t	X_{t-1}	X_{t-2}	X_{t-3}	X_{t-4}	X_{t-5}	X_{t-6}	X_{t-7}
1	0.069492	0.083356	0.159610	0.118017	0.104153	0.131881	0.187339	0.187339
2	0.083356	0.069492	0.083356	0.159610	0.118017	0.104153	0.131881	0.187339
3	0.048695	0.083356	0.069492	0.083356	0.159610	0.118017	0.104153	0.131881
4	0.076424	0.048695	0.083356	0.069492	0.083356	0.159610	0.118017	0.104153
5	0.124949	0.076424	0.048695	0.083356	0.069492	0.083356	0.159610	0.118017
6	0.118017	0.124949	0.076424	0.048695	0.083356	0.069492	0.083356	0.159610
7	0.124949	0.118017	0.124949	0.076424	0.048695	0.083356	0.069492	0.083356
8	0.118017	0.124949	0.118017	0.124949	0.076424	0.048695	0.083356	0.069492
9	0.097220	0.118017	0.124949	0.118017	0.124949	0.076424	0.048695	0.083356
10	0.090288	0.097220	0.118017	0.124949	0.118017	0.124949	0.076424	0.048695

11	0.166542	0.090288	0.097220	0.118017	0.124949	0.118017	0.124949	0.076424
12	0.228932	0.166542	0.090288	0.097220	0.118017	0.124949	0.118017	0.124949
13	0.228932	0.228932	0.166542	0.090288	0.097220	0.118017	0.124949	0.118017
14	0.166542	0.228932	0.228932	0.166542	0.090288	0.097220	0.118017	0.124949
15	0.173474	0.166542	0.228932	0.228932	0.166542	0.090288	0.097220	0.118017
16	0.159610	0.173474	0.166542	0.228932	0.228932	0.166542	0.090288	0.097220
17	0.228932	0.159610	0.173474	0.166542	0.228932	0.228932	0.166542	0.090288
18	0.235864	0.228932	0.159610	0.173474	0.166542	0.228932	0.228932	0.166542
19	0.270524	0.235864	0.228932	0.159601	0.173474	0.166542	0.228932	0.228932
20	0.263593	0.270524	0.235864	0.228932	0.159610	0.173474	0.166542	0.228932

4.1 Stock Price Forecasting using Neural Network (MLP) Model

The MLP architecture used in this study employs 7 neurons in the input layer. To evaluate the performance of the MLP model, we used an MLP with the following configuration:

a. Input Layer:

Number of Neurons: 7 neurons, corresponding to the number of input features used to train the model, namely 7 lag features (Close_Normalized_lag_1 through Close_Normalized_lag_7). Each neuron in the input layer receives a single feature from the normalized lag data.

b. Hidden Layers:

Number of Hidden Layers: randomly selected, 1 or 2 hidden layers.

First Hidden Layer: randomly selected with varying numbers of neurons: 30, 50, 64, 75, and 100 neurons

Second Hidden Layer: randomly selected with varying numbers of neurons, 25 and 50.

c. Activation Function:

The Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function is used in both of these hidden layers. The ReLU function helps introduce non-linearity into the model, allowing it to learn more complex patterns in the data.

Each neuron in the hidden layer is connected to all neurons in the previous and next layers. The number of neurons is a hyperparameter that can be adjusted to find the optimal balance between the model's ability to learn patterns and the risk of overfitting or underfitting.

d. Output Layer:

Number of Neurons: 1 neuron. Used to predict a single continuous value, namely Close_Normalized. This model uses solver='adam' as the optimization algorithm and is trained with max_iter=500 iterations, with random_state=42 for reproducibility.

In this study, the training and testing data were split into 80% and 20%, respectively, as previously done by researchers Gülmez (2023) and Teixeira & Barbosa (2025).

The following are the MAE, RMSE, and R^2 performance results of individual MLP models with the number of hidden layers and the number of neurons set to random values.

Table 4. Comparison of MAE, RMSE, and R² performances of the MLP model

No	MLP Model	Performances		
		MAE	RMSE	R ²
1	hidden_layer_sizes: (100, 50)	0.0424	0.0559	0.8039
2	hidden_layer_sizes: (100, 25)	0.0426	0.0579	0.7894
3	hidden_layer_sizes: (50, 50)	0.0407	0.0540	0.8168
4	hidden_layer_sizes: (50, 25)	0.0562	0.0744	0.6519
5	hidden_layer_sizes: (50,)	0.0454	0.0612	0.7645
6	hidden_layer_sizes: (100,)	0.0418	0.0564	0.7998
7	hidden_layer_sizes: (75,)	0.0430	0.0595	0.7774
8	hidden_layer_sizes: (64,)	0.0679	0.0922	0.4649
9	hidden_layer_sizes: (30,)	0.0477	0.0596	0.7769

Table 4 shows that the MLP model with a hidden_layer_sizes configuration of (50, 50) demonstrated the best overall performance, with the highest R² (0.8168), the lowest MAE (0.0407), and the lowest RMSE (0.0540). This confirms that the architecture with two hidden layers, each containing 50 neurons, is the most optimal among the tested configurations.

Regarding the performance of the single-layer MLP model, the hidden_layer_sizes (100) configuration (a single hidden layer with 100 neurons) also performed excellently, closely matching the best-performing hidden_layer_sizes (50, 50) configuration.

4.2 Stock Price Forecasting using MLP and Forward Selection

This study also employs the Forward Selection feature selection method to determine which features influence the target variable in the MLP model for the BCA stock closing price dataset.

For the BCA stock closing price dataset, the MLP model's performance improved significantly after applying Forward Selection. The performance results for integrating the MLP with the Forward Selection feature selection are shown in Table 5. The integration of the MLP and Forward Selection feature selection yielded the selected features, namely Close_Normalized_lag_1 and Close_Normalized_lag_2, which resulted in a significant performance improvement compared to the model trained with all seven lag features.

Table 5 also shows a comparison of the performance of the MLP model with 2 hidden layers, each containing 50 neurons, before and after integration with Forward Selection:

Table 5 Comparison of performance between the MLP and the proposed method

No	Model	Performances		
		MAE	RMSE	R ²
1	MLP (50,50) - All Features	0.0407	0.0539	0.8169
2	MLP (50,50) with FS	0.0331	0.0462	0.8658

Table 5 shows that the MAE decreased from 0.0407 to 0.0331 after applying the Forward Selection method. This means the mean absolute error (MAE) of the MLP model's predictions decreased, indicating improved accuracy. The RMSE value also decreased from 0.0540 to 0.0462. This decrease is significant because RMSE is more sensitive to large errors, indicating that the model with optimal features has more consistent errors. The most notable performance improvement is seen in the R² score, which rose from 0.8168 to 0.8658. This higher R² indicates that the model with optimal features explains a much larger proportion of the variance in the target variable (Close_Normalized). This confirms that the model has become better at forecasting stock closing prices.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of this study, the best model for forecasting BCA stock closing prices is the Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) with a hidden layer configuration of (50,50), integrated with the Forward Selection feature selection method. This model delivers optimal performance with an MAE of 0.0331, an RMSE of 0.0462, and an R² of 0.8658, indicating that the prediction error rate is relatively low and the model's ability to explain variance in the data is very good. The application of the Forward Selection feature selection method effectively improved the performance of the MLP model by reducing the feature set to the most relevant ones, namely Close_Normalized_lag_1 and Close_Normalized_lag_2. This not only improves prediction accuracy but also makes the model more efficient and stable by reducing the influence of less significant features. The integration of an optimal MLP architecture with appropriate feature selection can yield a forecasting model that is more accurate, consistent, and reliable for modeling stock prices.

References

- Bao, W., Cao, Y., Yang, Y., Che, H., Huang, J., & Wen, S. (2025). Data-driven stock forecasting models based on *Neural Networks*: A review. *Information Fusion*, 113, 102616. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2024.102616>
- Bommert, A., Sun, X., Bischl, B., Rahnenführer, J., & Lang, M. (2020). Benchmark for filter methods for feature selection in high-dimensional classification data. *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis*, 143, 106839. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csda.2019.106839>
- El Touati, Y., Slimane, J. B., & Saidani, T. (2024). Adaptive Method for Feature Selection in the Machine Learning Context. *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, 14(3), 14295–14300. <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.7401>
- Funde, Y., & Damani, A. (2023). Comparison of ARIMA and Exponential Smoothing Models in the Prediction of Stock Prices. *The Journal of Prediction Markets*, 17(1), 21–38. <https://doi.org/10.5750/jpm.v17i1.2017>

- Gao J. R-Squared (R²) – How much variation is explained? *Research Methods in Medicine & Health Sciences*. 2024;5(4):104-109. doi:[10.1177/26320843231186398](https://doi.org/10.1177/26320843231186398)
- Gülmez, B. (2023). *Stock price prediction with optimized deep LSTM network with artificial rabbits optimization algorithm*. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 227, 120346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2023.120346>
- Gao J. R-Squared (R²) – How much variation is explained? *Research Methods in Medicine & Health Sciences*. 2024;5(4):104-109. doi:10.1177/26320843231186398
- Jin, H. (2025). Data Time Spans Impact on Stock Price Prediction: An Empirical Study Across Multiple Markets Based on BP *Neural Networks*. *Advances in Economics, Management and Political Sciences*, 191(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.54254/2754-1169/2025.BJ24010>
- Kakkar, V., Pandey, D. C., Verma, V., Mehrotra, R., Singh, P., & Tiwari, R. (2024). Artificial Intelligence for Stock Prediction: A Bibliometric Review. 2024 1st International Conference on Innovative Sustainable Technologies for Energy, Mechatronics, and Smart Systems (ISTEMS), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISTEMS60181.2024.10560228>
- Khadka, P. B., & Karki, D. (2024). Bibliometric Analysis of Machine Learning Models for Stock Price Prediction. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 13(1), 116–141. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jis.v13i1.73347>
- Lakshmi, P. S., Deepika, N., Lavanya, V., Mary, L. J., Thilak, D. R., & Sylvia, A. A. (2022). Prediction of Stock Price Using Machine Learning. 2022 International Conference on Data Science, Agents & Artificial Intelligence (ICDAAI), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDAAI55433.2022.10028862>
- Liapis, G. I., Tsoka, S., & Papageorgiou, L. G. (2025). Optimisation-Based Feature Selection for Regression *Neural Networks* Towards Explainability. *Machine Learning and Knowledge Extraction*, 7(2), 33. <https://doi.org/10.3390/make7020033>
- Mahfuzh, M. F., & Yuliantari, R. V. (2022). Analisis penerapan artificial Neural Network algoritma propagasi balik untuk meramalkan harga saham pada Bursa Efek Indonesia. *Journal of Applied Electrical Engineering*, 6(1), 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.30871/jaee.v6i1.3814>
- Mandal, J. K., Mukhopadhyay, S., Dutta, P., & Dasgupta, K. (2020). Algorithms in Machine Learning Paradigms (Vol. 870). <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-981-15-1041-0>
- Nath, O., & Shakhari, S. (2023). Stock Market Prediction Techniques: A Literature Review. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, 11(1), 1793–1800. <https://doi.org/10.22214/ijraset.2023.48931>
- Otchere, D. A., Ganat, T. O. A., Ojero, J. O., Tackie-Otoo, B. N., & Taki, M. Y. (2022). Application of gradient boosting regression model for the evaluation of feature selection techniques in improving reservoir characterisation predictions. *Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering*, 208, 109244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petrol.2021.109244>
- Purwanto, Eswaran, C., & Logeswaran, R. (2011). Improved Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System for HIV/AIDS Time Series Prediction. In A. Abd Manaf, S. Sahibuddin, R. Ahmad, S. Mohd Daud, & E. El-Qawasmeh (Eds.), *Informatics Engineering and Information Science* (Vol. 253, pp. 1–13). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-25462-8_1
- Saputra, M., & Suharsono, N. T. (2025). Implementasi Metode Artificial *Neural Network* Untuk Memprediksi Harga Saham (Studi Kasus PT. BANK CENTRAL ASIA Tbk). *Jurnal Rekayasa Sistem Informasi dan Teknologi*, 2.
- Singh, T., Kumari, M., & Gupta, D. S. (2024). Rumor identification and diffusion impact analysis in real-time text stream using deep learning. *The Journal of Supercomputing*, 80(6), 7993–8037. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-023-05726-x>
- Suhartono. (2008). Feedforward *Neural Networks* for time series modelling. *Unpublished Doctoral dissertation*, Gajah Mada University, Indonesia
- Suripto, S. (2023). Decision-making model to predict auto-rejection: An implementation of ARIMA for accurate forecasting of stock price volatility during the Covid-19. *Decision Science Letters*, 12(1), 107–116. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.dsl.2022.10.002>
- Teixeira, D. M., & Barbosa, R. S. (2025). *Stock Price Prediction in the Financial Market Using Machine Learning Models*. *Computation*, 13(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/computation13010003>

- Usmani Mehak, Zulfiqar Ali Memon, Adil Zulfiqar, & Rizwan Qureshi. (2024). *Preptimize: Automation of time series data preprocessing and forecasting*. *Algorithms*, 17(8), 332. <https://doi.org/10.3390/a17080332>
- Wang, W., Lin, W., Wen, Y., Lai, X., Peng, P., Zhang, Y., & Li, K. (2023). An interpretable intuitionistic fuzzy inference model for stock prediction. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 213(PA), 118908. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2022.118908>
- Widhi Aryanti & Nur Azizah Komara Rifai. (2023). Penerapan Artificial Neural Network dengan Algoritma Backpropagation untuk Memprediksi Harga Saham. *Jurnal Riset Statistika*, 107–118. <https://doi.org/10.29313/jrs.v3i2.2953>
- Yahoo Finance. (n.d.). PT Bank Central Asia Tbk (BBCA.JK). Retrieved March 01, 2026, from <https://finance.yahoo.com/quote/BBCA.JK/>